

Название публикации: «**METAPHOR AND METONYMY AS MEANS FOR
SEMANTIC DERIVATION IN MODERN ENGLISH**»

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Abstract: This writing aims to learn the concepts metaphor and metonymy, defines the notion semantic derivation and express their characteristics in Modern English.

Studying the current literatures, observing the people who often use metaphor and metonymy during their daily speech, and considering its reason, this research will describe the origin and meaning of present symbolic words and the role of above notions in contemporary English. The results of this issue identifies the differences between metaphorical and metonymical meaning shifts with particular examples, access whether they have learned completely or not, their impact for effective discourse and identify the research gaps on this area.

Key words: Metaphor, metonymy, semantic derivation, meaning shift.

Since words appear, they express a particular notion but later due to the language processes, they convey symbolic meanings besides their original ones. Studying the Modern English language leads linguists to search the semantic derivation of particular words and phrases that had quite different meaning in previous times and their later changes into other concepts with the influence of using them in various

states. In these issues, analyzing the usage of metaphor and metonymy as the main figures of speech, some linguists consider that due to these devices some words replaced into various sense gradually. As narrators intend to reinforce the meaning of their discourse and attain quicker to the addressees, they use some shift in meaning and this time the most common figures of speech like metaphor and metonymy are mostly used. Actually, transferred meanings appear in the base of straight meanings of words in the use. Generally, the term “metaphor” came from Greek word “matapherein” that means “to bear” or “to transfer”. The main intention using a metaphor is comparing two distinct concepts or objects through a perceived resemblance. Unlike simile which uses the transitions “as” or “like”, this device links two diverse objects without using them. William Shakespeare’s phrase in his poem “As you like it” is a great instance to this device that “All the world is a stage, and all men and women merely players”. Here the playwright compares the life as a stage and people, who will be born and die, are actors of this stage. Furthermore, the origin of the term metonymy also related to Greek word “meta” and “onoma” that means to substitute of a name. Metonymy is the interdependence of events, things and a shift in meaning which is based on relationship. So the metaphor is used for substitution and comparing signs of similar objects while metonymy serves for association. In addition, although they have some external and internal features with each other, in metonymy the connections of two objects is compared. The concepts metaphor and metonymy led linguists to several studies and researches in all fields of linguistics. First of all, the Greek philosopher Aristotle acknowledged in his book “Poetics” followings “A metaphor is something that is not specify to a thing, gender, or species gender, or a generic or analogues word”. Later in 1980, the most important book was created on this topic. George Lakoff, a professor on Linguistics, and Mark Johnson, a

Professor at the University of Sciences and Arts, Oregon, who are known as coauthors of the book “Metaphors we live by”. This work indicates metaphor as the basis for humans’ thoughts and conveying their ideas in speech. Currently language researchers use this book as the main manual for learning conceptual metaphor and its types. Moreover, Tadshibova R., a lecture at Dagestan University, identified the origin of the term “semantic derivation” and studied metaphor as its wide-spread type in Modern English. Besides them, Ali Abdullah Ilah Ghan, Asst.

Lecturer in the Kufa University, considered the types of semantic conversion, metaphorical and metonymical shift of meanings and presented their correlational usage with selected instances. However, it is worth to say that all words that modified due to the concepts metaphor and metonymy was studied sufficiently. Every literary device is materialized with the help of language facilities. Therefore, it is essential to learn metaphor and metonymy from the linguistic and semantic point of view.

In the course of the historical development of a language, the meaning of a word may change. A metaphorical extension is an expansion of meaning in a new direction by initially popularizing the metaphorical meaning. Metaphorical expansion is a natural process that occurs with almost every word. Even this is not characterized as a change of meaning. The assertion of thought using metaphor is so ingrained in ordinary speech that the original metaphorical derivation of the meaning of some words is neglected or completely forgotten. A metaphor whose literal meanings have been forgotten is a “dead metaphor”. This contributes to the constant change of language over time during the process of metaphorical expansion and the subsequent death of metaphors. For example, the word “engine,” meaning “inborn talent,” derived from the Middle English ingen,

originally emerged as a metaphorical reference to things created by such talented people. Later, as this meaning began to be used in general, the original meaning of the word was lost. However, not all metaphorical expansions lead to the loss of the original meaning of words. English has many frozen metaphors and their original meaning can be easily found. Nevertheless, a speaker who uses a particular term may not consciously use its meaning. For example, although the usage of terms have a little association with the objects they refer, the meaning of technological terms can be easily found. People refer to the "face" and "hands" of a watch without feeling that they have personalized the watch, even though these terms were originally metaphorically derived from the personification of the watch.

Actually many words are used as metaphorical descriptive phrases but later collapse into general words gradually. The word “window”, for instance, firstly was

the description for the object “wind eye”. Even though people do not recognize “eye”

as a part of this word due to its metaphorical description of this object. Nowadays people no longer recognize this definition as a metaphor, and the “eye” is no longer seen as part of it (Neufeldt, 1991, p. 1530). The word “signal” can also be an example

of this process. The word is derived from the French word *alarme*, which in turn is derived from the Italian *all'arme*, which means "to arms" (Neufeldt, 1991, 30) In

Italian, the phrase means a metaphorical change. In fact, the phrase is derived from the words "call to arms (all'arme)" and has become a metaphor. The phrase “weapons,” which describes the name ‘bell’, stands metonymically for that name.

Collins Dictionary lists six meanings of the word “tea” and suggests this word to the process of metonymical meaning shifts.

- I. An evergreen shrub or smaller tree.
- II. The dried shredded leaves, used to make a beverage by infusion in boiling water.
- III. Any of various plants that are used to make tealike beverage.
- IV. Also called afternoon tea(a light meal eaten in the afternoon).
- V. Also called high tea (the main evening meal)
- VI. U. S. slang word for marijuana. (Collins Dictionary, 1979, 1940)

It can be seen here that the word tea metonymically and gradually extended its use from denoting a plant to the product, a drink, a special social occasion for inviting guests and finally a process where the whole family gather for eating and talking.

To sum up, the general approach of this research was to study and find the semantic origin of literary devices metaphor and metonymy, which are used in Modern English. As qualitative method is usually based on languages, observations and images this research used it in order to code and categorize the types of words in modern usage and their semantic source. It finds that it is essential to learn the book “Metaphors we live by” By George Lakoff to review the general knowledge about this theme. Then in order to find and compare past and

new forms of these devices, there is a need to search some special literatures of Old and Middle English periods as well as contemporary fictional books, diverse articles and linguistic journals round this topic. Besides, as we do not live in English speaking country, there is no opportunity to observe the real metaphorical and metonymical conversations directly. That is why, another styles of observing may be used. For example, to watch old and new versions of a film, observe online chats, study the British newspapers and magazines, and learn modern idiomatic dictionaries.

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